

Trace Metal Studies in Extractable Organic Matter (EOM) and Rock Samples of Cambay Basin

S. R. DALAL** and Y. K. AGRAWAL*

Analytical Laboratory, Pharmacy Department, Faculty of Technology and Engineering, Kalabhavan,
M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 001

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The metal ions, viz. vanadium, titanium, molybdenum, iron, nickel and zinc have been determined in the EOM (extractable organic matter) and source rock samples of Cambay basin, and the data is tested for geochemical distributions.

METALLO-organic complexes derived from biological material have been shown to occur in many types of sediments^{1,2}. It is believed that the majority of oil and gas occurrences and their presumed source rock and associated with sedimentary strata deposited during the period when there was an abundant life. Association of nickel and vanadium with several organic compounds in oil also suggests that the source material was derived from the decay products of the land plants. The introduction of nickel should be easier than that of vanadium due to its relative stability, and as a result, the recent sediments are richer in nickel than the ancient ones³.

Al-Shahristani and Al-Attiya⁴ measured 13 trace elements, Al, V, Cl, Ni, Mn, K, Zn, Ga, Na, As, Br, Hg and Co, in Iraqi oils. They concluded that vanadium and nickel content of an oil has a direct relationship with its history of migration and accumulation in North Iraq, the results providing evidence for vertical migration of oil in the Kirkuk and Alin Zalah oil fields.

All the metals detected in crude oil have been detected in the marine organisms, most of them being essential trace elements. One would expect that petroleum should reflect to some extent trace elements composition of living matter. In order to accomplish this, some authors proposed that the mean elementary composition of living organisms has varied in geological time and vanadium probably been a more common constituent of organisms in the past geologic time⁵. With this in view in the present investigation, the trace elements have been determined in the extractive organic matter (EOM) and sedimentary rock samples of Cambay basin.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR or G.R. grades.

The reagents *N*-phenyl-2-naphthohydroxamic acid (P-2-NHA), *N*-phenyl-*m*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid (P-*m*-MBHA) and *N*-phenylbenzohydrox-

amic acid (PBHA) for the determination of vanadium, titanium and molybdenum, respectively, were synthesised as described by Agrawal^{6,7}. Their 0.1% (w/v) solutions were used for extraction purposes. The standard solutions of V (50 ppm), Ti (50 ppm) and Mo (50 ppm) were prepared by dissolving requisite amount of ammonium metavanadate, titanium chloride and ammonium molybdate in 250 ml water in presence of hydrochloric acid and final concentrations were determined spectrophotometrically⁸.

A Shimadzu UV-VIS 240 spectrophotometer with 10 mm cell was used for photometric measurements. A GBC 901 atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used for common metal analysis.

Extracted organic matter (EOM): EOM or formation rock samples weighing around 50 mg were taken for decomposition with the mixture of acids. The samples were first dissolved in hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness. The samples were decomposed with 1 : 1 HNO₃ and HCl and evaporated to dryness. The resulting residue was treated with perchloric acid (5 ml; 68%, w/v) and hydrochloric acid (15 ml) and heated to dryness for decomposition of all organic matter in the sample. The sample was redissolved in hot 0.1 N HCl, filtered, cooled and diluted to 50 ml.

Determination of vanadium: The method is essentially the same as that described by Agrawal⁹ and a calibration curve was prepared in the range of 0.05–15 ppm of vanadium. Aliquots (5 ml) of the sample were taken in a separatory funnel and water (5 ml) was added to it. Then a 0.01% (w/v) solution of potassium permanganate was added dropwise until the contents retained a light pink colour (to oxidise vanadium to V⁵⁺) and then concentrated HCl (10 ml) and 0.1% NaF (5 ml) were added. The contents were shaken vigorously with 0.1% (w/v) P-2-NHA (10 ml) for 2–3 min and the layers were allowed to separate. The chloroform layer was drawn over anhydrous sodium sulphate for drying, and then transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask. The extraction was similarly

**Regional Chemical Laboratory, O. N. G. O., Baroda-390 009.

repeated with the reagent solution (5 ml) to ensure complete recovery of vanadium. The sodium sulphate was washed with chloroform, and the extract was diluted to 25 ml with chloroform in a volumetric flask. The absorbance was measured at 550 nm against the reagent blank.

Determination of titanium: The extraction method for the spectrophotometric determination of titanium was the same as that described by Agrawal¹⁰ and a calibration curve was prepared in the range of 0.5–10 ppm of titanium.

The sample (5 ml) was transferred to a 100 ml separatory funnel and 0.1% ferrous sulphate solution (5 ml) was then added to reduce V^V to V^{IV}. Then concentrated HCl (10 ml) and 0.1% (w/v) chloroform solution (5 ml) of the reagent (P-*m*-MBHA) were added. The mixture was shaken for 10–15 min and the chloroform layer allowed to separate. The resulting yellow extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove moisture and transferred to a 25-ml volumetric flask. To ensure complete recovery of titanium, the aqueous layer was further extracted with the reagent solution (2×5 ml) and sodium sulphate was washed with chloroform (3×2 ml) to remove the last traces of yellow colour. Finally, the extract was diluted to the mark. The absorbance of the yellow extract was measured at 410 nm against the reagent blank and titanium concentration was computed. The method for titanium was very rapid, and many commonly occurring metal ions did not interfere in the determination.

Determination of molybdenum: Molybdenum(vi) was determined spectrophotometrically as molybdenum-*N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid complex. The yellowish green coloured complex having λ_{max} at 395 nm obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.9–45 ppm. Mo was determined in presence of closely associated ions, viz. Ti, V and Fe. The method was simple and rapid and successfully applied for the determination of molybdenum in petroleum samples.

The method for the determination of molybdenum was essentially the same as described by Agrawal¹¹. The calibration curve was prepared in the range 0.9–45 ppm of Mo.

Into 125-ml separatory funnel, a standard molybdenum and petroleum sample (ashed; 5 ml) were transferred to a 125 ml separatory funnel and the acid strength of the aqueous media was adjusted to 2 *N* with concentrated HCl and water to a final volume of 50 ml. 2 ml of each solution of ferrous sulphate (0.1%, w/v) and sodium fluoride (0.1%, w/v) were added to mask V and Ti, followed by the reagent solution (PBHA; 10 ml), and the contents were shaken for 5–10 min. The organic layer was then separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and transferred to a 25-ml volumetric flask. The extraction was repeated with the reagent solution (2×3 ml) for the complete recovery of molybdenum. Finally, the sodium sulphate was washed with chloroform, washings were collected

in the same flask, and the extract was diluted to 25 ml with chloroform. The absorbance was measured at 395 nm and the molybdenum concentration determined from the calibration curve (by difference of the known concentration of standard molybdenum, molybdenum in unknown sample is evaluated).

Atomic absorptions spectrophotometric method: Calibration curves were prepared for each of the elements under study. The wavelength chosen for Fe, Ni, Zn, V, Ti and Mo were 248.3, 232, 213.8, 318.4, 364.3 and 313.3 nm, respectively. In case of V, Ti and Mo the determinations were carried out by standard addition method¹².

Results and Discussion

The ratio V/Ti falls (Table 1) within a narrow margin but not the ratios V/Ni, V/Fe and V/Zn. A set of correlation coefficients are computed for the free metal concentrations and the ratio of V/M with respect to °API gravity and pour point in degree centigrade.

TABLE 1—EOM AND SEDIMENT SAMPLES FOR TRACE METAL ANALYSIS

Sl. no.	Lab. Code No.	Well No.	Depth Interval m	Wt. of EOM taken mg	Wt. of sediment taken mg
<i>Mehsana area</i>					
(A) Jotana field					
1.	Jo-1	Jotana-5	1200–1225	52.1	650.5
2.	Jo-5	Jotana-5	1450–1500	35.6	600.8
3.	Jo-7	Jotana-10	1400–1450	42.8	580.9
4.	Jo-10	Jotana-10	1850–1900	32.7	695.5
(B) Lynch field					
5.	Ly-1	Lynch-2	1500–1525	62.1	688.5
6.	Ly-4	Lynch-2	1700–1750	158.9	690.6
7.	Ly-8	Lynch-3	1400–1450	66.0	696.5
8.	Ly-9	Lynch-3	1900–2000	57.4	686.5
9.	Ly-14	Lynch-3	3200–3250	41.4	598.9
10.	Ly-17	Lynch-4	1400–1450	41.4	614.4
11.	Ly-20	Lynch-4	2100–2150	36.8	598.8
(C) Sobhasan field					
12.	So-1	Sobhasan-66	1700–1725	53.0	599.8
13.	So-2	Sobhasan-66	1725–1750	110.3	602.7
14.	So-3	Sobhasan-66	1750–1775	61.1	631.5
15.	So-4	Sobhasan-66	1775–1800	90.6	650.3
(D) Santhal field					
16.	Sa-1	Santhal-8	1700–1800	33.0	642.8
17.	Sa-2	Santhal-8	2000–2100	40.6	645.9
18.	Sa-3	Santhal-8	2200–2300	51.7	660.3
19.	Sa-4	Santhal-8	2300–2400	79.8	662.7
(E) Other fields					
20.	Kh-1	Khervah-1	1375–1400	44.0	598.9
21.	Da-1	Dangarwah-1	1625–1675	46.6	635.8
22.	Ja-2	Jakasna-1	1950–2050	38.8	650.3
<i>Ahmedabad area</i>					
23.	Ka-1	Kalol-237	2200–2220	120.8	639.7
24.	Ka-2	Kalol-237	2220–2240	129.0	637.7
25.	Ka-3	Kalol-237	2240–2255	93.1	690.3

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TABLE 2—TYPICAL ANALYSIS OF TRACE ELEMENTS IN EOM CAMBAY BASIN

Sl. no.	Lab. Code No.	Concn. of elements ppm						Relative ratio of vanadium to metal				
		V	Ti	Mo	Ni	Fe	Zn	V/Ti	V/Mo	V/Ni	V/Fe	V/Zn
<i>Mehsana area</i>												
(A) Jotana field												
1.	Jo-1	4.8	4.4	4.6	0.4	1.6	6.5	1.10	1.04	12.13	3.03	0.75
2.	Jo-4	4.8	4.7	4.7	0.8	0.4	9.5	1.02	1.02	6.00	12.00	0.50
3.	Jo-7	5.8	4.6	5.0	3.0	1.6	5.5	1.26	1.16	1.93	3.64	1.05
4.	Jo-10	8.2	6.6	7.0	6.5	8.5	13.2	1.26	1.17	1.26	0.96	0.62
(B) Lynch field												
5.	Ly-1	8.2	6.6	7.0	4.5	10.5	12.5	1.24	1.17	1.82	0.78	0.68
6.	Ly-4	7.9	5.9	6.8	1.8	3.5	13.5	1.34	1.16	4.38	2.25	0.59
7.	Ly-8	4.8	4.2	4.5	6.5	6.0	6.5	1.14	1.07	0.74	0.80	0.74
8.	Ly-9	7.5	5.8	6.3	7.5	8.0	4.4	1.29	1.19	1.00	0.94	1.66
9.	Ly-13	8.4	7.2	8.0	16.0	13.5	9.5	1.16	1.05	0.53	0.45	0.88
10.	Ly-17	7.4	6.9	7.2	1.6	2.5	6.0	1.07	1.03	4.63	2.96	1.23
11.	Ly-20	9.0	6.9	8.2	6.5	4.5	0.8	1.30	1.10	1.38	2.00	11.25
(C) Sobhasan field												
12.	So-1	9.5	6.8	7.5	7.2	16.0	0.9	1.40	1.27	1.32	0.59	10.55
13.	So-2	9.5	6.5	8.0	0.4	2.5	6.5	1.38	1.13	22.5	3.60	1.38
14.	So-3	9.2	6.6	8.2	0.8	2.7	6.6	1.39	1.12	11.5	3.33	1.39
15.	So-4	9.0	6.5	7.9	0.9	2.7	6.6	1.38	1.14	10.0	3.33	1.37
(D) Santhal field												
16.	Sa-1	10.0	5.2	8.5	0.6	6.8	3.2	1.92	1.18	16.66	1.47	3.17
17.	Sa-2	10.5	5.6	8.8	10.5	1.8	2.02	1.19	1.00	1.05	5.83	5.83
18.	Sa-3	10.8	6.0	9.0	12.0	32.0	4.0	1.80	1.20	0.90	0.34	2.70
19.	Sa-4	10.9	6.0	9.2	18.0	1.7	4.5	1.82	1.18	0.61	6.41	2.42
(E) Other fields												
20.	Kh-1	9.5	7.5	8.1	5.8	3.3	0.9	1.26	1.17	1.64	4.13	10.56
21.	Da-2	4.6	4.0	4.4	0.8	18.0	2.5	1.15	1.05	5.75	0.26	1.84
22.	Ja-2	5.1	4.3	4.7	3.5	—	6.7	1.19	1.09	1.46	—	0.76
<i>Ahmedabad area</i>												
23.	Ka-1	4.2	3.0	3.6	8.0	6.5	1.40	1.17	0.53	0.65	0.65	8.40
24.	Ka-2	4.4	3.0	3.8	2.5	0.5	10.0	1.47	1.16	1.76	8.80	0.44
25.	Ka-3	4.4	3.2	3.9	6.5	1.9	1.8	1.38	1.13	0.68	2.32	2.44

TABLE 3—TYPICAL ANALYSIS OF TRACE ELEMENTS IN ROCK SAMPLES OF CAMBAY BASIN

Sl. no.	Lab. Code No.	Concn. of elements ppm						Relative ratio of vanadium to metal				
		V	Ti	Mo	Ni	Fe	Zn	V/Ti	V/Mo	V/Ni	V/Fe	V/Zn
<i>Mehsana area</i>												
(A) Jotana field												
1.	Jo-1	8.90	7.40	6.4	0.40	4.70	9.40	1.20	1.39	22.25	1.89	0.95
2.	Jo-4	8.80	8.70	7.7	1.10	0.80	12.50	1.11	1.14	8.00	11.0	0.70
3.	Jo-7	10.00	8.60	9.0	6.00	4.60	8.50	1.16	1.11	1.66	2.17	1.17
4.	Jo-10	12.50	9.50	10.3	10.50	11.50	16.20	1.31	1.21	1.19	1.09	0.77
(B) Lynch field												
5.	Ly-1	12.30	10.70	11.0	4.0	6.30	24.40	1.15	1.12	3.10	1.95	0.50
6.	Ly-4	12.00	9.90	10.9	6.20	7.50	19.50	1.21	1.10	1.94	1.60	0.62
7.	Ly-8	13.00	8.80	11.9	11.30	12.00	13.50	1.48	1.09	1.15	1.04	0.96
8.	Ly-9	11.50	9.50	10.4	12.20	13.50	8.50	1.21	1.19	0.94	0.85	1.35
9.	Ly-13	14.00	12.20	12.8	21.60	23.40	14.70	1.14	1.09	0.65	0.60	0.95
10.	Ly-17	12.00	11.90	10.9	5.20	5.50	11.30	1.00	1.10	2.31	2.18	1.06
11.	Ly-20	14.00	15.30	12.4	15.50	8.90	1.50	0.92	1.13	1.22	1.57	9.33
(C) Sobhasan field												
12.	So-1	15.50	14.90	14.4	10.80	21.30	3.40	1.04	1.03	1.44	7.31	4.56
13.	So-2	14.60	10.80	13.5	1.40	7.50	11.50	1.35	1.08	10.42	1.95	1.27
14.	So-3	15.60	12.30	14.5	10.20	7.30	5.80	1.27	1.03	1.53	2.14	2.69
15.	So-4	14.80	12.40	13.7	10.50	7.00	5.50	1.19	1.03	1.41	2.11	2.64

(Table 3 contd.)

(D) Santhal field

16.	Sa-1	15.30	9.80	14.2	5.60	11.80	8.50	1.56	1.08	2.73	1.30	1.80
17.	Sa-2	15.50	10.20	14.4	15.50	16.20	7.30	1.51	1.07	1.00	0.96	2.13
18.	Sa-3	15.40	11.00	14.3	17.30	40.10	9.50	1.40	1.07	0.89	0.98	1.63
19.	Sa-4	16.00	10.90	14.9	22.60	6.70	10.70	1.47	1.07	0.71	2.39	1.54

(E) Other fields

20.	Kh-1	13.50	11.60	12.4	10.70	7.20	1.10	1.16	1.09	1.29	1.88	13.27
21.	Da-2	8.60	7.70	7.5	4.40	5.10	5.70	1.12	1.15	1.95	1.63	1.61
22.	Ja-2	8.20	8.50	7.0	6.30	7.50	21.50	0.96	1.17	1.30	1.09	0.38

Ahmedabad area

23.	Ka-1	9.60	9.40	8.5	6.20	14.30	5.90	1.02	1.13	1.55	0.67	1.63
24.	Ka-2	8.80	8.50	7.6	13.00	11.40	5.50	5.50	1.04	1.16	0.68	0.77
25.	Ka-3	9.40	8.40	8.3	7.50	6.50	15.50	1.12	1.13	1.25	1.45	0.61

Vanadium concentration varies between 4 and 10 ppm, titanium between 4 and 6 ppm both in the EOM and sedimentary samples. The metal concentration is higher in sedimentary rock compared to the EOM samples in all the cases. The relative ratio (Tables 2, 3) of vanadium to titanium is also within the narrow range 1.2–2.0, while the variations V/Fe and V/Ni are larger. The ratio V/Ni does differ much. Generally, the age of the oil and the producing reservoir rocks are believed of the same age¹³.

In the present investigation we find a trend in the range of values of vanadium and titanium which are related to the petroleum formation conditions at some geological time¹⁴.

Even though the ratio of V/Fe and V/Ni are large, the correlation coefficients of these ratios with respect to the physical properties (°API gravity) and pour point (°C) show a good agreement (Table 4). The ratio V/Ni seems to be closely responsible for composite constituents in the crude oil and the characteristic changes of pour point of the crude. The metamorphism of petroleum crude generated in the geological period is presumably governed by the concentration of these two elements. Zinc shows a good correlation with respect to gravity and pour point¹⁵.

Vanadium and nickel are reported to be present as porphyrin complex and as naphthenates in petroleum. More than one type of vanadium-porphyrin complex and free porphyrins have been identified in petroleum¹⁶. The position of vanadium in porphyrin complex¹⁷ is said to be responsible for the various properties of crude oil including the viscosity of crude petroleum. In view of such wide difference in the concentration of sedimentary vanadium and titanium and the petroleum bound concentration of these elements, it is difficult to conceive of a total relationship between sedimentary petroleum bearing rocks and the crude petroleum matrix in terms of their paragenesis and age. This can be further evidenced only by a detailed study of the proportion of these elements in the petroleum bearing reservoirs, that is a lateral or vertical variation in concentration of these elements in the host rocks¹⁸.

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TABLE 4—CORRELATION OF PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF OIL WITH TRACE METALS IN EOM OF CAMBY BASIN

Area/Parameters	Gravity °API	Pour point °C
Jotana	39.64	37.0
Lynch	33.95	43.5
Santhal	16.08	0.0
Sobhasan	29.43	27.5
Kalol	36.08	34.77
Vanadium	-0.588	-0.798
Titanium	-0.836	-0.605
Nickel	-0.872	-0.903
Iron	-0.550	0.523
Zinc	0.543	0.4163
V/Ti	-0.139	-0.293
V/Ni	0.147	0.102
V/Fe	-0.179	-0.858
V/Zn	-0.975	-0.945

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